

resistance scales of these types are significantly lower than that of other types. In terms of average resistance, Yunnan rices could be classified into three significantly different resistance groups.

Presence of rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) in xylem cells of tungro-infected rice

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Earlier studies have shown that RTBV and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) are restricted to the phloem tissues of infected plants, and it has been suggested that only phloem feeding by green leafhopper (GLH) causes tungro infection. On GLH-resistant cultivars, however, it has been observed that GLH feeds mainly from the xylem and transmits primarily RTBV. We examined the location of RTBV in host cells in relation to tungro transmission.

Rice seedlings (15 d old) of tungro-susceptible cultivar TN1 and GLH-resistant cultivar ASD8 were inoculated with rice tungro viruses (RTVs) using adult GLHs. The leaf blades of infected plants were collected 30 d after inoculation for electron microscope study.

RTBV particles were found in xylem parenchyma cells as well as in phloem

Table 2. Distribution of resistant varieties in 8 classes and the significance level test of mean resistance scales.

Classification	Total (no.)	Resistant varieties		Mean resistance scale ^a
		no.	%	
Indica-irrigated-nonglutinous	1832	65	3.55	8.02 b
Indica-irrigated-glutinous	303	17	5.61	7.76 b
Indica-upland-nonglutinous	31	0	0	8.35 a
Indica-upland-glutinous	20	1	5.00	7.80 b
Japonica-irrigated-nonglutinous	679	70	10.31	7.38 c
Japonica-irrigated-glutinous	419	50	11.93	7.26 c
Japonica-upland-nonglutinous	641	24	3.74	7.96 b
Japonica-upland-glutinous	166	15	9.04	7.39 c
Total	4091	242	5.92	

^a Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different.

cells of tungro-infected TN1 and ASD8 (see figure). RTSV was observed only in phloem cells and around the boundary between xylem and phloem tissues. In initial observations, RTBV in xylem cells were found in the third and fourth leaf position of infected plants.

These results suggest that GLH can transmit RTBV directly to xylem cells, where the virus multiplies and causes infection. They also support the observation that GLH feeds mainly from the xylem of GLH-resistant cultivars and transmits predominantly RTBV. □

RTBV in xylem parenchyma cells of rice cultivars TN1 (a) and ASD8 (b). R = ribosomes.

Integrated germplasm improvement—upland

Four upland rice varieties released in Sierra Leone

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The uplands account for about 70% of the rice area in Sierra Leone. In 1988, four new varieties (ROK17, ROK18, ROK19, ROK20), all foreign introductions, were released for upland planting (Table 1). These varieties surpassed check variety ROK16 in overall performance and farmer acceptability in field tests over four seasons.

Table 1. Mean performance of 4 newly released varieties in Sierra Leone.

Variety	Original name	Height (cm)	Duration (d)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Mean grain yield (t/ha)
ROK17	LAC23	119	138	186	3.1
ROK18	IDSA-6	96	117	174	2.9
ROK19	FARROX 299	116	115	172	2.8
ROK20	IRAT161	103	118	178	3.0
ROK16	NGOVIE (local)	128	132	183	2.6

In varietal trials conducted for two seasons in farmers' fields in three villages in the North-Western Region, the new varieties consistently outyielded local check ROK16. Table 2 shows grain yields and some properties of the soils.

ROK17 is a local japonica selection from Liberia. It is a medium-duration cultivar, with bold grains much like ROK16. It is, however, more resistant to diseases and lodging than ROK16 and is suited to the high rainfall areas of East

Table 2. Yield of 4 new upland rice varieties in farmers' fields in Kambia District, Sierra Leone.

Variety	1986-87				1987-88			
	Kamaranka	Funkia	Petifu	Mean	Gberika	Rochain	Rochint	Mean
ROK17	2.2	1.9	2.1	2.1	2.9	2.4	2.4	2.5
ROK18	2.0	2.8	2.3	2.4	2.8	2.8	2.3	2.4
ROK19	2.8	2.3	2.0	2.2	2.4	2.0	2.3	2.2
ROK20	2.4	2.1	2.3	2.3	2.7	2.2	2.4	2.3
ROK16 (check)	1.8	1.6	1.8	1.7	1.5	1.3	1.7	1.5
CV (%)	12.2	14.6	18.2	15	19.7	22.9	14.4	19
LSD (0.05)	8.2	8.2	8.2	8.2	8.2	8.1	8.2	8.2
Soil	Sandy loam	Loam	Gravelly clay loam		Clay loam	Sandy loam	Loam	
pH (water)	5.0	4.9	5.1		5.5	4.8	5.0	
CEC (meq/100g)	11.4	10.2	13.2		15.1	9.9	11.1	
Organic C (%)	1.2	0.9	1.4		2.1	0.8	1.8	
Total rainfall (mm)	2,156				2,256			

and South Sierra Leone. ROK17 is preferred by North Sierra Leone farmers because it is awnless, which makes threshing with the feet less painful. It also has better cooking and eating qualities.

ROK18, ROK19, and ROK20 are short-duration varieties superior to ROK16 in plant type, disease resistance, and phenotypic acceptability. They are recommended for the low rainfall areas of the north. Grain size ranges from slender to medium bold, as preferred by northern farmers. □

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

ASD18, a blast (Bl)-resistant rice variety for Tamil Nadu

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Bl-resistant, short-duration, medium-slender rice culture AS34011, selected from the cross ADT31/IR50, was released as ASD18 by the Tamil Nadu G.D. Naidu Agricultural University in Jan 1991. It is recommended as an alternative to IR50 and TKM9 for summer (Mar-Jun), first season (Jun-Sep), and second season (Nov-Feb) planting.

ASD18 is 90 cm tall with 105-110 d growth duration. Mean grain yield was 7.3 t/ha over 6 yr at RRS, 5.7 t/ha in multilocation trials over 2 yr at seven research stations throughout Tamil Nadu, and 5.9 t/ha under Adaptive Research Trials (ART) in 52 farmers' fields. Total dry mass was 18.2 t/ha (8.5 t grain and 9.7 t straw) at Ambasamudram; potential grain yield was 10.1 t/ha under ART.

It is resistant to Bl and moderately resistant to sheath rot and tungro (Table 1). It is resistant to brown planthopper and stem borer and moderately resistant to gall midge and leafhopper (Table 2). □

Table 1. Reaction of ASD18 to major diseases in Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Reaction ^a						
	Blast			Sheath rot ASD-N	Sheath blight ASD-A	RTV	
	ADT-A	DBE-A	ASD-N			ADT-A	CBE-A
ASD18	1	3	3	5	7	4	5
IR50	3	9	9	7	9	5	3
TKM9	3	7	7	7	9	8	9

^aBy the Standard evaluation system for rice (SES) scale. N = natural condition, A = artificial condition, ADT = Aduthurai, ASD = Ambasamudram, CBE = Coimbatore.

Table 2. Reaction of ASD18 to major pests in Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Reaction ^a						
	BPH		SB		GM	LF	
	ADT-A	ASD-A	ASD-N	MDU-A	MDU-A	CBE-N	ASD-A
ASD18	3	5	3	0	5	7	5
IR50	9	5	3		3	9	7
TKM9	9	9	3		0	9	7

^aBY SES. BPH = brown planthopper, SB = stem borer, GM = gall midge, LF = leafhopper. ADT = Aduthurai, ASD = Ambasamudram, MDU = Madurai, CBE = Coimbatore. N = natural condition, A = artificial condition, (-) = not tested.

Integrated germplasm improvement—rainfed lowland

Three new varieties of short-duration rice released in Cambodia

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Short-duration rices (120 d or less) cover almost 25% of Cambodia's rice area. In the dry season, they are grown in about 10% of the area, either irrigated or with receding water. In the wet season, they are grown in about 15% of the area as a rainfed lowland crop.

A number of traditional early varieties